

ETHNOPHARMACOLOGICAL STUDY ON THE HEALING KNOWLEDGE OF THE INDIGENOUS PEOPLE IN DESIGNING SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL IN-PLANT TAXONOMY

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the ethnobotanical documentation of medicinal plants and the healing knowledge of indigenous people which served as basis in designing supplementary material in teaching Plant Taxonomy. In doing this, the ethical and legal considerations were first ensured. The ethnobotanical survey was conducted by using a semi-structured interview with six (6) informants, all were traditional folk healers and medicinal herbs vendors. Based from the gathered data, fifty-one (51) plant species were identified and were then classified into 38 families. The families most represented were Annonaceae, and Moraceae with three species each, followed by families of Graminae, Lamiaceae, Malvaceae, Meliaceae, Menispermaceae, Myrtaceae, and Zingiberaceae with two species each, and the rest of the families were represented by only one species. The 51 plant species were used to treat 28 different diseases. The most important and widely used medicinal plants were the species *Acorus calamus* L. and *Euphorbia hirta* Linn. which has the highest use value of 1.16. From the data gathered, 15 or 29.41% of the medicinal plants were used for treating fever. Decoction or boiling of leaves was the most commonly used method of preparation and this was taken orally. The study suggests that medicinal plants can meet the essential medical care needs and was able to preserve the culture, particularly the knowledge in indigenous healing, beliefs, ways, and healthcare practices, of the Ayta Indigenous Cultural Community of Barangay Tongko, Tayabas City, Quezon.. These findings offer baseline information which can be used to further develop the preparations of these medicinal plants in order to advance the indigenous health system and drug discovery, thus recommending an ethnopharmacological study as future research direction. Moreover, the documentation of medicinal plants that parallels to systematics and classifications as well as traditional uses of plant taxa led to designing a supplementary material in teaching Plant Taxonomy.

Keywords: Ayta ICC, Ethnobotanical Study, Healing knowledge, Supplementary material